

Lab tips, tricks and hacks: Storing and/or shipping air sensitive 2D materials

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The new 2D materials beyond graphene and transition metal dichalcogenides are typically air sensitive. Good examples of that are black phosphorus, the new family of magnetic 2D materials or the layered hybrid perovskites.¹⁻⁴ This might be a particularly serious issue when a collaborative research is being carried out and the samples fabricated in one lab have to be sent somewhere else to be measured. High vacuum suitcases are extremely expensive and cumbersome, and they might not be actually needed in most cases.

We have developed a protocol to store and/or ship air sensitive 2D materials. We employ a **Sico 250 Premium vacuum sealer** to seal our sample boxes within hermetic plastic bags at 100 mbar. As this vacuum level is not good enough for certain air-sensitive 2D materials we introduce in the vacuum bags [oxygen absorber](#) and a [silica gel](#) (to remove remaining moisture) sachets. See **Figure 1**.

Oxygen absorbers (sometimes referred to as oxygen scavengers) are used in the food industry adding them to enclosed packaging to help remove or decrease the level of oxygen in the package. Oxygen absorber sachets are typically made of a mixture of iron oxide and sodium chloride powder.

Table 1. Summary of the components needed for the storage/shipping process of environmentally sensitive 2D materials.

Vendor	Description	Unit price
www.envasadoravacio.com	Vacuum sealer Sico 250 Premium - 400 w. 0,9 bar. 20 l/min.	259.00
Amazon	O2frepak 50cc (300-Pack) – Oxygen absorbers	15.99
Amazon	200-Pack Silica Gel	4.87
Total:		279.86 €

Figure 1. Pictures of the vacuum sealer and the oxygen absorber and silica gel sachets.

We have tested the performance of the oxygen absorber sachets by sealing an oxygen sensor in a big plastic bag at atmospheric conditions containing several O2frepak sachets. We observed that the oxygen level drops in matter of minutes and after a bit more than one hour the oxygen level is below the detection limit of the oxygen sensor (0.05%). See **Figure 2**. And we have checked that the oxygen level remains below the detection limit for (at least) more than one month.

Figure 2. Testing the oxygen absorber sachets with an oxygen sensor.

Table 2. Oxygen sensor purchasing info.

Vendor	Description	Unit price
Amazon	Oxygen sensor	89.00

References

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